

Lempi: “do you remember that moment there?” Nonverbal stories of memorable locations in long-distance relationships

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Abstract Nonverbal communication (*NVC*) is the richest way for people to emotionally express themselves. However, in computer-mediated communication (*CMC*) *NVC* is underused. People in long-distance relationships (*LDRs*) already know how to adapt to *CMC*. While *CMC* is considered to be less ideal, *LDRs* still have a tendency to disclose more intimacy, closeness and relatedness to each other than non-*LDRs*. As *CMC* has been mainly designed for business purposes, there is an opportunity to target relatedness experiences and a challenge to find inter-relatedness of the daily activities of *LDRs*. The key question is: Which attributes do *NVC*-products need to have to evoke an enriched experience of relatedness for *LDRs*?

This phenomenological research exposes meaningful experiences and stories that can be expressed via adaptation to *NVC*. Prototypes were built via iterations around *NVC*-product attributes to trigger intended relatedness experiences. The diary study and in-depth interviews disclosed a broad range of valuable stories about feeling related at a distance. Suggestions are made on how to apply these attributes and stories when designing for both richer verbal and nonverbal communication experiences. The attributes and stories of Lempi are also useful for further research to deeper understand how people can communicate in more meaningful ways.

Keywords *Nonverbal communication, Long-distance relationships, Relatedness, Meaningful locations, Experience design*

Introduction

Communication is necessary to be maintained within any relationship (Aylor, 2003). One experiences closeness and intimacy by disclosing feelings and emotions to each other. People want to connect regularly with others who care about them to feel intimate and fulfill the need of relatedness (Sheldon et al., 2001, p. 339, cited in Hassenzahl, Heidecker, Eckoldt, Diefenbach, & Hillmann, 2012).

Intimacy requires two components: the sharing of emotions and inter-relatedness of daily activities (Guldner, n.d.). Nonverbal communication (*NVC*) is the easiest way to express emotional and relational information that is not present in spoken and written language (Trenholm, 1999). “Our nonverbal behavior towards someone is heavily influenced by the bond we feel with the other person” (Janssen, IJsselsteijn, & Westerink, 2010 p. 3). This is also described in the equilibrium theory by Argyle (1965): “The closer people are related to each other, the more nonverbal behavior is possible to be exchanged. When a stranger intrudes you personal space nonverbal behavior will change to keep the balance in the intimacy equilibrium.”

Technology focuses on the transmission of explicit information while subtle and emotional cues, typical for close relationships, are neglected (Hassenzahl et al., 2012). Couples in long-distance relationships

(*LDRs*) engage in more adaptive self-disclosure and form more idealized relationship perceptions than non-*LDR* couples do in the pursuit of intimacy across various computer-mediated communication (*CMC*) (Jiang and Hancock, 2013). Nevertheless, “inter-relatedness” remains a challenge (Guldner, n.d.).

People can connect differently through *NVC* (Triverio, 2011). *NVC* helps when partners do not have any stories to tell but they just want to feel close to each other when physically separated (Hassenzahl, 2011) and it can increase relatedness experience (Janssen, Bailenson, IJsselsteijn, & Westerink, 2010).

Implementing *NVC* provides a new medium with possibilities for new adaptations and future usage. This can radically improve the comfort and quality of the communication experience (Janssen, IJsselsteijn, & Westerink, 2010). Solutions should be “communication experiences” orientated rather than “mobile devices” (Hassenzahl, 2011). Hassenzahl (2010, p.8) defines an experience as: “an episode, a chunk of time, that one went through, sights and sounds, feelings and thoughts, motives and actions closely knitted together, stored in memory, labeled, relived and communicated to others. Experience is a story, emerging from dialogue of a person with her or his world through action”

Figure 1. Theoretical framework with attributes listed.

Research objective

This research aims to guide design for nonverbal relatedness experiences, the affective episodes or stories in which *LDR* partners feel close, related and intimate without using words. It is important to facilitate these experiences over a distance. The objective is to find out which attributes are necessary to evoke NVC experiences that make people feel related at a distance. The research studies the ways of getting the daily mundane untold stories told in a nonverbal way. This has been challenging within *CMC*, where functionality is mostly prioritized (Hassenzahl et al., 2012).

Attributes

For this study, more than 150 different physical and digital artifacts were evaluated, majority gathered by Hassenzahl et al. (2012). The different strategies for relatedness experiences cover awareness, expressivity, physicalness, gift giving, joint action and memories (Hassenzahl et al., 2012). The strategies help to see where there is a need for further research and development. This study takes into account also social psychology theories, such as uncertainty reduction theory, which focuses on “verbal and nonverbal communication between recipients and providers that reduces uncertainty about the situation, the self, the other, or the relationship” as noted by Albrecht and Adelman (1987, p. 19). Without managing relational uncertainty an interpersonal relationship cannot be sustained (Dainton & Aylor, 2001; Knobloch & Solomon, 1999). Uncertainty reduction ensures that partners commit and plan for a mutual future.

The artifact analysis resulted in product attributes that give guidance on how to design for a NVC experience. Attributes are tools for developing novel and improved concepts. They were listed within their

related field of study in a theoretical framework (Figure 1).

Artifact analysis highlighted the feasibility of the following attributes in particular. *Rich interaction* claims that physical interaction can be designed in such a way it is perceived intuitively, by unifying form, shape and interaction (Frens, 2006). This makes interaction meaningful with a possible extension to the message.

To make people change their behavior products need to stage an experience and be transformational (Halfon, 2007). Experiences can make people communicate in a different way. The *aesthetic of friction* (Hassenzahl, 2011) points out that experiences are transformational in themselves. These pleasurable troublemakers mock the multi-capable user by establishing a friction between your current and desired behavior (Hassenzahl & Laschke, 2015). Products with *hedonic quality* facilitate achievement of fundamental human needs, those beyond instrumental and action needs, such as being a caring partner and a part of each other’s life.

A *personal device* connects two partners together, like a ring. No one else has a similar device; it is unique and symbolizes the bond between the two. Yet, it is not an alarm going off and it always known who is sending the message. Being notified is not overwhelming. Such *unobtrusive* notification does not interrupt *Tangible* memories (Hassenzahl et al., 2012) are of great importance as by touching the object one can re-experience a mutual moment. Thus, one can get closer to the partner in a relative way through touching the product

Figure 2. Xsound Surprise effect, Secret language.

Figure 3. Xstress Support / Care, Simultaneously, Communal relationship.

Figure 4. Xplore Old reference, Daily routines.

Figure 5. Xview Old reference, Rich interaction.

Figure 6. XDancer Equity theory, Reciprocity.

Figure 7. Xtrude Related representation and participation, Simultaneously.

See them in action: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLB0t8O0gQfOo8vfa9Asi3zyck3havD9-L>

Figure 8. A set of Lempi devices.

A NVC device is preferably wearable or hand-held instead of a stationary object or immense installation. The contact with the product resembles the contact one wants to have with the partner, near and carried along. With an *intimate mobile* device, one is not restricted to a certain location and the device can document the fresh experience.

Addressing a *different sense*, from vision, enables capturing experiences in novel ways, achieving a broad contact through other channels of NVC.

Instead of passive monitoring or demanding scheduling events, the product helps to register and *log* events during the day. Afterwards the user can select the most representative events.

In the case of *old reference*, new functionality is added to an old, out-of-use product. The general usage of the artifact is clear, as the artifact already familiar. The usage fits within users' mind-set and due to the original device it can add a nostalgic or romantic vintage feeling to the product.

A *secret language* makes the "conversation" more engaging. Certain devices enable a new language between the users on a rudimentary level some allow complex coding. However, these intimate and confidential messages are not explicit as in "virtual sex". Communicating in a way that is open for interpretations results in more freedom for creating meanings in an *abstract way*.

X-series

After selecting the most promising attributes based on previous research, a series of concepts was developed (Figure 2 – 7) to evoke a wide range of relatedness communication experiences, called the X-series.

The concepts were derived through a Design Inclusive Research (Horvath, 2007) process where experiences were tested through iterations. The combination of attributes that were embedded within the products were tweaked and adjusted to strengthen the NVC experiences, to become crystalized and to be expressed in a successful combination. People in *LDRs* and design experts expressed their feelings and opinions on the six prototypes as part of the verification. Figures 2-7 show the X-series concepts and their attributes.

Lempi

Lempi means favorite, love, and fondness in Finnish language. The product Lempi derives from one of the X-series' products, Xplore, that communicates location and memories.

Lempi makes you dare to deal with your long-distance relationship. It challenges the situation of being apart and may even emphasize this separation. However, Lempi also gives positive insights on locations. The issue with long-distance is not only the physical separation but also the mental separation: one usually does not know what the other one is experiencing today, the partners do not know the favorite places of each other, one does not have mutual everyday experiences to talk about.

Lempi enables storytelling by reporting about location-related experiences and emotions (*intimate mobile*), and thus links partners' daily life (*daily routines*). Lempi aims to create content between the partners in their remote environments and thus build a bridge across the distance (*closer*). One can tag (*logging*) memorable and hopeful locations (uncertainty reduction theory) that are linked to the couple. The other way round, the user gets *unobtrusive*

Figure 9. Attributes embedded within Lempi.

Figure 10. Lempi user instructions (to see Lempi in action https://youtu.be/_bLLhfYo56g).

Day 1

date:

Store one important location

- Pull the bottom out while holding the pointer up.
- Value your mood matching the location by turning the bottom clockwise.
- Push in the bottom to store the location.

Why did you choose this location?

Why did you give it this value?

Which other locations would you like to store? And why?

What are your first thoughts / impressions on Lempi concept?

Where do you store Lempi?
when at home:

when on the road:

How often do you think about Lempi?

How often do you come across Lempi?

Problems regarding the usage?

Figure 11. Diary, day 1 task and questions.

color-coded notifications, surprises (*surprise effect*) and gets more familiar with the partner's daily life. Lempi can lead to interesting conversations and questions to know each other better, resulting in more engaging and meaningful communication. Lempi is also a companion that helps the user to feel safe and comforts when being stressed or missing the partner. It takes the users to those places where they feel close (*hedonic quality*). In addition, via Lempi the partners can give each other tips and recommendations about the locations in their environment. Lempi guides the user to these locations when nearby next time (*different sense*).

Lempi is small, round, simple and ambiguous (*abstract*). The build of it is robust and reliable. The aesthetics of form already evokes emotions: the compass-shape follows the idea to an *old reference*. The *rich interaction* is implemented in its simple handling; each action mode requires a different orientation of the product towards the user. Unlike with an application on a laptop or a phone, one can touch and feel Lempi as a separate sacred and *personal device*.

The meaningful content of the stories is stored within the product, waiting to be re-experienced (*tangibility*) later on when *LDRs* meet in person, to make those moments even richer.

Methodology

Phenomenological method

The goal of this study is to design for experiences and thus the study uses a phenomenological research method. As Fokkinga & Desmet (2012, p.3-4) suggest, there are certain conditions that allow the participants share their experiences, stories and opinions openly: There should be no prejudice and the researcher should be equally interested in each topic touched upon by the participants

A diary study was chosen as a qualitative research method to simulate how the product would fit into users' daily lives and to get feedback on their emotions during this study. The aim is to achieve subjective perceptions, as these triggered NVC experiences and the stories they are embedded in cannot be achieved otherwise.

A diary study is a quick and inexpensive way of obtaining real-world data about peoples' behavior and experiences. The researcher gets the opportunity to witness subtle behavior as the participant can note activities they may not otherwise recall in a typical research interview. In addition, the diary study is followed by an in-depth interview to give more insight into their past experiences.

Sample

Four couples from different types of *LDRs* were recruited. They were selected based on different parameters such as how much time and distance they are apart. Two couples live in the same country but had different schedules, seeing each other only during weekends, while the other two meet less often than once a month, showcasing more extreme *LDRs*.

The participants were between 20 and 35 years old. Born between 1980-1995, they have grown up with the rapidly advancing technology within ICT, Internet and mobile computing. Thus, they are adapted to different *CMC* technologies such as Skype, email and Facebook to connect.

A non-probabilistic judgmental sample method was used. The population was contacted through social media channels, which also functions as sampling criteria: The participants need to have adapted to some social media to be able to show some adaptation to Lempi as well. The sample is non-representative and limited in size. However, for the purposes of this study, the sample size and the sampling method were considered sufficient.

store

Storing one location

Go to the location/environment you want to store.

Pull the bottom out while holding Lempi vertical with the pointer up.

Value your experience matching the location by turning the bottom clockwise. You can do this according to the colour or to the amount of the LEDs that light up.

Push in the bottom to store the location. The LED ring turns off now

As this is a simulation, please check-in at this location via foursquare as well

Figure 12. Manual.

Diary study

In the diary study participants reflect on their communication behavior and experiences for seven days. The study was done using *Foursquare application* (now *Swarm*, by *Foursquare*) as the fully-functional prototypes were not available at the time due to problems with programming the prototype. *Foursquare*, a social media application for location sharing, provided a suitable solution for the diary study. The participants were instructed to use the application with a new account connected only with their partner, simulating the use of *Lempi*. For instance, when checking in to a location they were asked to write a number or color, related to the location, with notifications turned on for *Foursquare*. The mock-up experiment with *Foursquare* had certain downsides, such as the message being written, instead of using color-coded lights. In addition, *Foursquare* is an application embedded within a phone, not a separate device. For the study, the users were given a non-functional prototype of *Lempi* that looks like a finished product but does not function.

The use of the diary was first explained with a short survey. The study includes response scales that are used in varying ways as the users have different perceptions. However, scales are compared only within one participant's answers (MacKerron, 2011). The daily assignments in the diary stimulate the use of *Lempi* in all its aspects, storing and revisiting experiential, meaningful and memorable locations. At the end, there was a survey for the participants to reflect on the past experiences.

The participants got a manual explaining the simulation through *Foursquare*. The exact interaction of *Lempi* was explained in detail to ensure that participants got the best possible idea of *Lempi* during the simulation.

Interview

The in-depth interview clarified beliefs, argumentations, vision, opinions, behavior and experiences with a focus on the couple. The interview was semi-structured, enabling analyzing the patterns of the different diaries. The participants were interviewed in person or via Skype.

First, the participants were asked to reflect on how *Lempi* works to know how the participants interpret and understand *Lempi*. For a more structured view, the participant chose 5 cards best describing the experience and 5 that are not related at all out of a 50-carddeck (Emotional response cards by Azeim, 2012).

At the end, the other concepts from the X-series were presented and they were asked how they feel about those in comparison with *Lempi*.

Analysis

The diaries and interviews were summarized, formatted and coded in a thematic analysis, focusing on the words and expressions that helped evoke the NVC relatedness experiences. Through an analysis of the experiences described by the participants, the most important attributes were abstracted.

Results

Response

The 8 participants completed 52 daily assignments in total. There were differences between the participants and the relatedness experiences evoked, as well as regarding the reflections on NVC. All of them used various types of CMC to communicate on a daily basis. Their decisions on using these channels were based on cost and ease of use and less on the evoked relatedness experiences. They were adapted to CMC

such as leaving *Skype* on while they were working.

Acceptance of the prototype

The first impressions varied significantly, which resulted in different ways of accepting Lemp: Some reflected on the usage of the item and even question the use, value, technology or existence of Lemp. An application and faster interaction would be more justified. Consequently using Lemp required more attention from them, as they were confused about the communication that Lemp facilitates.

Others reflected on the meaning, seeing Lemp as romantic and theatrical. They expected a 90's mobile phone but got something entirely different. Consequently, they keep Lemp exposed. They show their friends what they got and tell them they like it. One participant got a comment from a friend "I almost hoped I was in a long-distance relationship so I could try this!"

The other X-series concepts were seen as more futuristic solutions. They give answers to questions participants did not even ask themselves. They feel that Lemp understands their need: the craving for different ways to express themselves. The interview proved the participants have a fair to good understanding of how Lemp would function.

After seeing the multiple possibilities of NVC in the X-series' scenarios all participants wanted to have their own communication customized, primarily by adding different channels to the communication. The wishes included physical contact, multi-colored messages, communicating more activities at once, or sound recordings connected to a certain location, in order to know each other's environment better.

One participant came up with the idea to take a picture and share how beautiful a place was at that certain moment. *Visual messages* seemed tempting for many participants, as it enables capturing experiences on the spot from their perspective.

Some would justify the usage of Lemp if it could function as a *logbook* and give an on-demand overview. *Logging* allows Lemp to be an ideal tracker for trips. Both partners have more freedom though capture the experience on the right moment. They could document the journey and reports are sent when connection is available. Also as a holiday planner Lemp helps to organize and remember places where people want to go together.

Relatedness Experiences

For some participants Lemp did not make them feel like being part of each other's life by reporting on their own activities, though they did feel so when getting more insight into their partner's daily activities. They wanted to get recommendations for locations from each other. Locations as such are not experienced as meaningful and instead they felt being monitored.

Others felt strongly emotionally connected. Receiving messages is perceived as valuable because the notifications make them feel that they are thinking of

each other. This more concrete emotional connection is also expressed by *re-experiencing* certain moments in *tangible* places. There is an increased interest in each other when storing and receiving locations. Lemp is seen as an empathic friend that can pass your feelings to your partner. Lemp will never be anything *obtrusive* as they recognize other tools for urgent matters, such as a phone call or sending a text message.

Finally some participants felt having Lemp *mobile* helps already to feel close, and forgetting Lemp would be the same as leaving behind their partner as it embodies and connects them. As long as Lemp is with their partner they will be notified through this medium, the other one will be all right in Lemp's company. They see Lemp as a *personal device*, carefully crafted and selected only for them. When they do not visit enough locations a feeling of guilt emerges, as *equity* is lost. Lemp *supports* them in being apart.

Usage

Mainly due to busy schedules participants went to look for special or pleasant activities within their *daily routine*. However, they did not want to report about work, as they do not want their work life to be involved in their intimate communication. It seemed sufficiently satisfying to just *surprise* each other with the activity or the location that the other one does not know about. This creates more interest, which can contribute a conversation as they start wondering what is meaningful about that location. The behavioral change can be seen as nonverbally enriched, as more mutual curiosity is generated.

When some participants are together over the weekend they store a *shared experience* together at a party they attend, to *memorize* for later.

Some participants store locations that have to do with an upcoming change in their life. They look for *future plans* in their environment next to their daily activities. One couple had ideas of going to certain locations, preferably together.

Another couple stored beloved locations as both partners could *escape* from their daily rush to be in some place where they feel at peace and related.

Meanings

The notification in itself is already a message as the participants saw what their partner felt when receiving the message. These color-coded messages made possible many meanings that only the partners understood. This *abstract* form also helped expression in different ways; Lemp gives more information by only location and an amount of LEDs. Every couple generated their own *secret language* through Lemp as the couples adapted to using Lemp.

By linking *mood* to a location, participants got empathic about each other's day-to-day live. For instance, they did not know how valued some places were to the other one. A certain mood could be communicated more straightforward in a pure way,

without being biased by the communication channel. Lempi has also worked as a part of a show-off game: They tell how well they are doing and how great the experiences are even without the partner. This way Lempi can turn into a competition. However, it can also feel like being monitored or getting jealous.

Some put more stress on the *activity* than on the location. For instance, they tell in different shades of red how well they ate at a restaurant. In their coding, each color stands for a different activity, with varying intensity. They adapted their communication and gave it meaning in their own way.

The feeling of getting closer was even perceived in different ways. Communicating the *distance* makes the time spend together more meaningful as they are separated from each other. Lempi is comforting and supportive. As the device itself already evokes the feeling of care and comfort, it can link this feeling to certain places. The *old reference* to a compass makes the concept clear and easier to adapt to the *guidance*.

The story told through the product is of great importance and it can increase the functionality of Lempi, even though just the product as such has meaning. When the concept of Lempi was further explained at the end of the interview, the prototype was perceived even better and the participants felt more understood by Lempi. The *old reference* made Lempi familiar and everyone has used an item that resembles Lempi, which does not mean they are still using it. It helps building the relatedness experience, as there are expectations how the product should be used. One couple perceived Lempi and its form accessible. Participants enjoyed the *rich interaction* of Lempi by turning its control, as it has a round shape, even though it does not function at all.

Transformations in behavior

Lempi is challenging as it gets in the way, one has to think of an extra item and take it along. This way Lempi was used as a reminder for the unwanted behavior of forgetting things. Lempi is a slightly less able and naïve product that has the *hedonic quality* for good and wanted habits such as pursuing a healthy lifestyle by going to the gym.

The role of distance is frustrating and creates a *friction* between being together and apart. With Lempi the content of the connection is the distance, the exact thing that prevents them from seeing each other when they need mutual support the most. This way Lempi underlines how important it is to be together. Lempi is difficult, as it does not have diverse meanings at once, compared to the other available media. Lempi feels like slowing them down.

This way, Lempi makes them stop during the daily rush and take time for a Zen-moment to reflect on the relationship and being a couple. A peaceful spot is preferred to escape mentally to the seaside, being immersed in the environment that is open, quiet and beautiful. Another participant teleports mentally to his partner, making him feel physically closer. For many, Lempi is seen as a companion that needs to be

taken care of.

Lempi stimulates a *different sense* for many participants, the sense of place and direction (Jacobs, J., et al., 2013), by making them aware of their relationship spatially. Participants discovered that their environment is full of meaningful places, unfamiliar to the other one, when they are confronted by the specific previous experience in that location. One participant wanted more of these meaningful locations around her to create a network to feel close to her partner or storing objects, such as a car and sofa, location seen as *safe locations*.

Discussion

According to the results, attributes vary in their ability to evoke NVC relatedness experiences and the ones with the strongest impact are shown in Figure 13. For instance, notifications need to be of an *unobtrusive* kind. When a partner is notified the meaning, linked to a certain location in Lempi's case, is already communicated. Users can decide whether to check it immediately or later. Acceptance of notifications varies and acknowledging the differences can help to understand the partner's communication preferences. Using *secret language* showed interesting adaptation to Lempi and highlighted how a couple became intimate through Lempi.

Addressing a *different sense* is intriguing because it makes people aware that they have the ability to communicate and perceive in a different way. By using Lempi a sense of place, direction and orientation is addressed, making the participants more aware of their environment. In addition, the usage of locations confronted the participants with each other. They did not know that some places had so much meaning for the other.

As in the case of Lempi, it is beneficial to not focus on screens, as they are already omnipresent. Screens are useful for sending explicit information, but also hard to use and demand very direct information. Contrary to that, the core idea is to leave some openness for interpretation, to allow ambiguity. One could argue that Lempi is too ambiguous for an aesthetical interaction but it was built as an open and unique platform for partners to facilitate and research expressivity. The interaction was the medium to achieve the experience. The interaction should not take the forefront compared to the experience one gets from the communication with the partner. The focus is not on the interaction with the product itself.

The method used includes problems. For instance, all participants were in a similar stage, not married nor with children. Their future perspectives were alike: within a month they were united again, at least for some time. This could have lead to the perception they were about to end their *LDR*, with better times were ahead. Due to such parameters and with the non-probabilistic judgmental sample used, the results are not to be generalized. Nevertheless, the results can help to understand other *LDRs* as well as NVC relatedness experiences.

Figure 13. The attributes with the most potential to evoke NVC relatedness experiences.

All participants knew the researcher, which eased talking about personal matters in a relaxed atmosphere but could be a source of bias. The participants were asked to be honest, critical and to express their doubts. A longer study would provide more knowledge, but will be more fruitful only when the prototype is fully functional and a more critical reflection on the embedded experiences is done (Hassenzahl et al., 2012).

Implications for future research and designs

To develop new NVC experiences, it needs to be taken into account that people have diverse preferences and by only providing one option of communication many people will drop out. Thus a product service system is desirable, starting from a basic product that can be extended over time, as both partners get to know their NVC capabilities better.

Location matters within LDRs and thus further research could deal with how places evolve along with the relationship, how they got their meaning and how this meaning fades or grows fonder. There are also other promising ways of addressing different senses, such as through scent, airflow and taste. Gesture technology such as kinetic tools or wristbands could help to develop this further.

The interaction should be recognizable so that the CMC channel does not evoke frustrations towards the technology itself and being unintentionally reflected on their partner. It also helps to make it attractive and acceptable. This is mainly the first step towards liking the product but also continues further on during the use of the product itself.

Conclusions

This study focuses on the ways a location can create

meaning, and hence not on the meaning a location has in a relationship. The chosen locations are meaningful, contributing to knowing each other better. Locations motivate questions leading to a conversation. The necessity of verbal communication is a positive consequence, not a drawback. It is beneficial because partners have more interest in each other, willing to know more. On a daily basis it is engaging to tell about yourself and make your partner aware of your experiences and stories. In addition, it contributes to future planning setting the scene for the next meet-up.

Attributes should not be haphazardly implemented; they need to be embedded within a story with a significant role in it. An imbalance between the story and the attributes results in weaker Relatedness Experiences. A next step could be more advanced storytelling practices.

People are not products you get intimate with by pressing a button or turning a switch. New meaningful interactions need to be explored and used instead of widely used existing product related interactions. New ways of NVC are interesting but sometimes artificial. They are less culturally influenced and do not try to imitate the real contact, done by using different terms such as orientation, direction and length of the NVC. There is no urge for simulation of the reality, but rather for new and subtler ways of meaningful connection.

Simulations are seen to replace real life meetings, and thus the product becomes a replacement of the real person and meetings would feel the same as the separation. New ways of nonverbal communication are sought so that the separation gives new experiences that are not possible while being together.

“Many authors appear to be aware of this difficulty (the lag that comes with technology) and therefore suggest a symbolic or poetic interpretation, rather than a one-to-one representation of physical intimacy, that is to replace physicalness with expressivity” (Hassenzahl et al., 2012, p 30:9)

Prototyping, such as with Lempi in this study, helps to find meaningful stories in research. Certain elements of Lempi can be used for future storytelling design. With Lempi the meaning is created by real life experiences. Nevertheless, you have to experience the story first to be able to relive the meaning.

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